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IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component

PLC γ 2 In Vitro Micelle Assay Using the Hydrophobic C16CF3-coumarin

Substrate

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Introduction

1-phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-2 (PLC γ 2, PLCG2) is an enzyme that converts PIP2 (phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate, PtdIns(4,5)P2, PI(4,5)P2) into IP3 (1D-myo-inositol 1,4,5-trisphosphate) and diacylglycerol (DAG). PLC γ 2 is mainly expressed in immune cells and microglia, but only sparsely expressed in other brain cells such as astrocytes and oligodendrocytes.[1] A rare coding variant in PLC γ 2, Pro522Arg (P522R) was identified from an Alzheimer's disease genome-wide association study (GWAS)[2] and replicated in various populations.[3,4,5] This mutation was found to confer a protective effect where patients who carried this P522R mutation exhibited a slower rate of cognitive decline than patients who did not.[6] While the exact mechanism of this protective effect of the P522R PLC γ 2 mutant is not fully understood, this mutation does induce a slight increase in enzymatic activity.[1] Therefore, pharmacologically intervention that increases the wild-type PLCG2's activity may provide a therapeutic strategy to lessen the cognitive decline in Alzheimer's disease patients.

At the time of writing, published literature described only two molecules that activate phospholipase C (PLC) enzymes in vitro, U73122 (1-(6-((17 β -3-methoxyestra-1,3,5(10)-trien-17-yl)amino)hexyl)-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione) [7] and m-3M3FBS (2,4,6-trimethyl-N-(meta-3-trifluoromethyl-phenyl)-

benzenesulfonamide) [8]. U73122 has been shown to activate PLC β and PLC γ family members in vitro [7], but it was originally identified as an inhibitor of PLCs.[9] In fact, U73122 was extensively used as the prototypical inhibitor of PLC enzymes in cell culture.[10,11,12,13,14] However, more recently U73122 has also been shown to effect numerous other cellular proteins including phospholipase D [15], 5-lipoxygenase [16], calcium channels [17], potassium channels [18], telomerase [19], histamine H1 receptor [20], and sarco/endoplasmic reticulum Ca²⁺-ATPase.[21] This complete lack of specificity is not surprising as the maleimide in U73122 can react with the thiol present in cysteine residues. Therefore, it is highly likely that U73122 non-specifically reacts with exposed cysteines on numerous proteins within a cell. This lack of specificity and high reactivity make U73122 a poor option to base a medicinal chemistry campaign with the goal of developing selective PLC γ 2 activators.

m-3M3FBS was originally identified from a screen of compounds that enhanced superoxide-generating activity in human neutrophils [8]. This activity was proposed to be caused by the direct activation of PLCs.[8] Supporting this proposition, several labs have shown that the downstream signaling effect of PLC activation – intracellular calcium release, was observed in various cell types treated with m-3M3FBS.[22,23,24,25,26] However, the potency and specificity of PLC activation of m-3M3FBS has been called into question as there are reports that intracellular calcium release occurs before any PLC activity is detected[27] and that m-3M3FBS effects the inward and outward flow of ions in a PLC-independent manner possible through the direct inhibition of delayed rectifier potassium channels.[28] Additionally, m-3M3FBS has been shown to be cytotoxic in some cell lines.[23,24,25] Currently, it is unclear if m-3M3FBS exerts its activity primarily through PLC activation and if it does, whether a derivative could be identified that is selective for PLC γ 2.

As no selective small molecule activators of PLC γ 2 are currently known, there is a clear need to identify such an activator to determine whether the pharmacological activation of PLC γ 2 is a viable therapeutic strategy to treat Alzheimer's disease. Fortunately, there are enzymatic assays that have already been developed that are amenable for high-throughput screening (HTS) [29,30]. These assays were primarily developed to identify inhibitors of PLC enzymes, [31] but these assays and substrates can be readily modified to screen for PLC γ 2 activators. These assays can be broadly classified into two groups. The first utilizes a water-soluble substrate epitomized by WH-15 that measures the catalytic activity of PLC enzymes in solution, [29] while the second uses a hydrophobic substrate such as XY-69 that imbeds in a micelle or liposome to measure the activity of PLC enzymes at a surface interface that better mimics the natural membrane-bound substrate PIP₂ [30].

As reported in the IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component PLC γ 2 Micelle and Liposome Substrate Synthesis – C16CF3C, the TREAT-AD Center synthesized a more hydrophobic WH-15 derivative with enhanced fluorescent properties. In this resource document, we detail the protocol of using this newly synthesized C16CF3-coumarin substrate to monitor the activity of PLC γ 2 on micelles. This substrate and generalized protocol should be amenable to other phospholipase C enzymes as well.

General Protocol

General Procedures of PLC γ 2 Micelle Assay Using C16CF3-coumarin

This PLC γ assay with the substrate was prepared by modifying previously reported methodologies (29). PLC γ 2 wild-type (WT) was expressed and purified by the Mesecar lab at Purdue University. Expression and purification conditions can be found in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6562203>.

Necessity of Sodium Cholate Micelles for the C16CF3-coumarin Substrate Reactivity

C16CF3-coumarin

In order to verify that the PLC γ 2 enzymatic activity upon the C16CF3-coumarin substrate was dependent upon the presence of sodium cholate micelles, the enzymatic activity was determined in the presence and absence of sodium cholate.

To accomplish this, enzyme and substrate solutions were prepared in micelle assay buffer (MAB; 50 mM HEPES, 70 mM KCl, 3 mM CaCl₂, 3 mM EGTA, 2 mM DTT, 0.5% W/V sodium cholate and 0.04 mg/ml of fatty acid free BSA, pH 7.4). A general protocol for the C16CF3 micelle assay was developed by modifying the solution assay protocol to determine the enzymatic activity of PLC γ 2 proteins on substrate embedded in micelles as described below:

1. 1 μ M of PLC γ 2 WT (20 mM HEPES, 150 NaCl, 5 %v/v glycerol, 1 mM DTT) was diluted with micelle assay buffer (MAB: 50 mM HEPES, 70 mM KCl, 3 mM CaCl₂, 3 mM EGTA, 2 mM DTT, 0.5% W/V sodium cholate and 0.04 mg/ml of fatty acid free BSA, pH 7.4) to yield a final protein concentration of 0, 5, 10 and 20 nM.
2. 1 mM of C16CF3-coumarin in water was diluted with MAB (50 mM HEPES, 70 mM KCl, 3 mM CaCl₂, 3 mM EGTA, 2 mM DTT, 0.5% W/V sodium cholate and 0.04 mg/ml of fatty acid free BSA, pH 7.4) to yield substrate concentration of 10 μ M.
3. 10 μ L of PLC γ 2 WT (0, 5, 10 and 20 nM) and 10 μ L of C16CF3-coumarin (10 μ M) were plated in the wells of a black 384-well microtiter plate. The final concentrations of PLC γ 2 WT and C16CF3-coumarin are 0, 2.5, 5 and 10 nM and 5 μ M in 20 μ L of total volume, respectively.
4. The plate was placed on a plate reader and its fluorescence intensity (ex: 362 nm; em: 496 nm) was recorded every 2 min for 60 min.

Initially, the ability of PLC γ 2 to enzymatically process the C16CF3-coumarin substrate was tested in the presence or absence of cholate micelles (i.e. a solution assay or micelle assay). As shown in **Figure 1A**, when no sodium cholate is present (i.e. PLC γ 2 solution assay), PLC γ 2 is essentially completely unable to process the C16CF3-coumarin substrate, as expected. However, when 0.5% W/V (~11.6 mM) sodium cholate is added, which is above the critical micelle concentration (~6-7 mM in HAB buffer), the C16CF3-coumarin substrate is efficiently processed by PLC γ 2 in a dose-dependent manner (**Figure 1B**). This data strongly suggests that the C16CF3-coumarin substrate needs to be incorporated into micelles to be efficiently processed and the reaction is likely occurring on the micelle interface, more closely mimicking the physiological conditions where the natural substrate, PIP-2 is embedded in the cell membrane.

(A) Solution Assay versus Micelle Assay **(B) C16CF3-coumarin/PLC γ 2 Reactions in Micelle Assay**

Figure 1. Enzymatic profiles of C16CF3-coumarin (5 μ M) for PLC γ 2 WT. (A) Enzymatic reactions of C16CF3-coumarin in solution, where no cholate is present and micelle assay, which contained 0.5% (W/V) cholate. (B) Enzymatic reactions of C16CF3-coumarin with various concentrations of PLC γ 2 (0-10 nM) in micelle assay.

Validation of PLC γ 2/C16CF3-coumarin Reaction in the Micelle Assay Using the PLC γ 2 Inhibitor, ATP (adenosine triphosphate)

To validate the C16CF3-coumarin for enzymatic reactions of PLC γ 2 in the micelle assay, ATP was utilized as an inhibitor. Various concentrations (0-100 mM) of ATP were prepared with water. PLC γ 2 WT (5 nM) and C16CF3-coumarin (10 μ M) were prepared with MAB as described above. 1 μ l of ATP solution (0-100 mM) and 10 μ l PLC γ 2 WT (5 nM) were added to the 384-well plate and incubated for 15 min at room temperature. After incubation, 10 μ l of C16CF3-coumarin (10 μ M) was added. Final concentrations of

Figure 2. Titration of ATP for PLC γ 2/C16CF3-coumarin in micelle assay. (A) Enzymatic reaction curves of PLC γ 2/C16CF3-coumarin in various concentrations of ATP and (B) Titration profile of ATP.

ATP, PLC γ 2 WT and C16CF3-coumarin are 0-4.8 mM, 2.4 nM and 4.8 μ M in a total volume of 21 μ l, respectively. Fluorescence intensity from enzymatic reactions was monitored with ex: 362 nm and em: 496 nm, as described above. The slope of reaction curves in the initial linear range (60 min) was used for analysis. As shown in **Figure 2**, ATP inhibited the enzymatic activity of PLC γ 2 in a dose-dependent manner (IC_{50} : 3.1 mM).

Kinetics Studies for C16CF3-coumarin Cleavage by PLC γ 2 in the Micelle Assay.

To further characterize the C16CF3-coumarin substrate, the kinetic parameters of the cleavage of C16CF3-coumarin by PLC γ 2 were determined in the micelle assay. PLC γ 2 (10 nM) and multiple concentrations of C16CF3-coumarin (0-50 μ M) were prepared with MAB as described above. 10 μ l of PLC γ 2 (10 nM) were added into the wells of a 384-well plate followed by a dispensing 10 μ l of the C16CF3-coumarin substrate (0-50 μ M). The final concentrations of PLC γ 2 and C16CF3-coumarin are 10 nM and 0-25 μ M, respectively in a total volume of 20 μ l. Fluorescence intensities from the enzymatic reactions were monitored with ex: 362 nm and em: 496 nm, as described above. The slope of the reaction curves in the initial linear range (60 min) was used for analysis.

Various concentrations of C16CF3-coumarin showed enzymatic reactivity with 10 nM of PLC γ 2 in dose-dependent manner which is represented with concentrations of hydrolyzed CF3-coumarin in **Figure 3A**. The K_m of PLC γ 2 for C16CF3-coumarin was 4.6 ± 0.8 μ M with a V_{max} of 0.019 ± 0.001 pmol/min/ng for the micelle assay (**Figure 3B**). These results suggest that the novel compound, C16CF3-coumarin, is feasible as a reporter substrate to determine the enzymatic activities of PLC γ 2.

Figure 3. Kinetic studies of C16CF3-coumarin and PLC γ 2. (A) CF3-coumarin produced by PLC γ 2 with various concentrations of C16CF3-coumarin (μ M) and (B) Michaelis- Menten plot for C16CF3-coumarin and PLC γ 2.

Application of PLC γ 2 and C16CF3-coumarin Reactions for High Throughput Screening (Z'-score):

Figure 4. Z' factor determination for HTS in pilot screen. Blue color, enzyme control (1X protein concentration); red color, activation control (2X protein concentration); green color, inhibition control (no protein).

total volume of 20 μ l, respectively. Fluorescence intensity from enzymatic reactions was monitored with ex: 362 nm and em: 496 nm, as described above.

The Z' scores for inhibition and activation control were 0.646 and 0.081, respectively. These results suggest that the optimized micelle assay of PLC γ 2 using C16CF3-coumarin substrate is excellent for screening of inhibitors and feasible for the screening of activators.

To establish the optimized assay conditions of C16CF3-coumarin and PLC γ 2 for high throughput screening, a Z' factor was determined in a pilot screen (**Figure 4**). In the screen, 0 nM and 5 nM of PLC γ 2 were used as inhibition and activation controls, respectively. PLC γ 2 (0, 5 and 10 nM) and C16CF3-coumarin (10 μ M) were prepared in the MAB as mentioned above. 10 μ l of PLC γ 2 enzyme concentrations of 0, 5, and 10 nM were added to the 384 well plate. The reaction was initiated by adding 10 μ l of the C16CF3-coumarin. The final concentrations of PLC γ 2 and C16CF3-coumarin are 0, 2.5, 5 nM and 5 μ M in a

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